

Research

EFFECT OF NUTRIENT SOURCE ON SOIL FERTILITY AND PRODUCTIVITY OF COWPEA [*Vigna unguiculata* (L) WALP.]

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Abstract: A greenhouse experiment was conducted at Pokhara, Nepal during summer of 2018 to access the effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on soil fertility and productivity of cowpea. The experiment was carried out in a completely randomized design with eight treatments and three replications. The treatments included eight selected combination of organic and inorganic nutrient sources (Farm yard manure, Vermicompost, Poultry manure, Nitrogen Phosphorous and Potassium). The physio- chemical properties of soil, nutrient uptake on yield attributes, yield and growth parameters were analyzed during the investigation . Result indicated that soil soil fertility has been improved where the OM was increased from 2.28-3.6% and P from 25.58 to 28.87 mg/kg in treatment containing organic fertilizer while soil pH and N% showing no significant difference among treatments. Maximum N, P and K content in seed and straw was obtained with 50% N from vermicompost @ 0.9t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer , however pod weight, pod girth , straw yield, 100 seed weight were found non –significant. Among growth parameters, 50% N from vermi compost @ 0.9t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer enhanced the growth parameters like plant height, number of leaves per plant. However number of branches, fresh weight of roots, nodules per plant was found non significant.

Keywords: Cowpea, Nutrient source, Soil fertility, Growth, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Legumes are important source of dietary protein and have unique ability of maintaining and restoring soil fertility through biological nitrogen fixation as well as addition of ample amount of residues to the soil. Legumes are mostly grown in Nepal as a source of human and animal protein

and it also enriches the nitrogen in soil to maintain soil fertility. Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*), an annual legume, also commonly referred as Southern pea. is an important source of food, income and livestock feed and forms a major component of farming systems because of its ability to improve marginal lands through nitrogen fixation and as cover crop.

Soils of the most parts of Nepal are acidic and is deficient in phosphorus, potash, and micronutrients like B, Zn, and Mo (Tuladhar et al., 2004). Further low-input agricultural production systems and poor agronomic management practices, limited awareness of communities and absence of proper land-use policies have aggravated soil fertility degradation. Likewise the application of mineral fertilizer to cowpea in Nepal is not common due to several socio-economic constraints such as the poor financial status of farmers

Integrated soil fertility management strategies include the combined use of soil amendments, organic materials and mineral fertilizers to replenish soil nutrient pools and improve the efficiency of external inputs. Therefore, to maintain the soil fertility and to supply plant nutrients in balanced proportion for optimum growth, yield and quality of crop with integrated approach is to be practiced under specific agro-ecological situation through the combined use of inorganic and organic sources of plant nutrients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study was carried out at Pokhara, Kaski during summer of 2018 inside a translucent plastic rain shed using plastic pots. Study site was located at an altitude of approximately 900 m above mean sea level with a latitude of 28°28'11"N and longitude of 83°93'80"E with average summer temperature of 20 to 25°C, average winter temperature of 9.2°C and average annual precipitation of about 3474 millimeters. The experiment was conducted in complete randomized design with eight treatments and three replications, each treatment conducted on an earthen pot of 8.5 kg capacity filled with soil alone and/or mixed with soil and/or inorganic or organic depending upon the type of treatment. The soil used for the was sandy clay in texture, slightly acidic in reaction (pH 6.24), medium in organic carbon (3%), medium in available nitrogen (0.24%), medium in available phosphorus (26.4 mg/kg) and high in potassium (109.7mg/kg) content. In each pot, five seeds of cowpea variety malepatan-1 were sown. One week after germination, plants were thinned to one plant in each pot. Urea (46% N) was used as the source of nitrogen, Diammonium Phosphate (18%N and 46% P) was used as the source of phosphorus and Muriate of Potash (60%

K₂O) was used as the source of potassium. Likewise, seeds were inoculated with rhizobium using standard method. Similarly, vermicompost was produced by using earth worms and the same inputs i.e., cattle manure and straw as bedding for the vermicomposting and bulking in the composting process. Samples were collected from well decomposed farmyard manure, poultry manure and vermicompost before they are applied. Then their N, P and K contents were analyzed in the laboratory using standard procedure to determine the rate of application of each treatment, which was based on recommended N equivalent rate for the test crop.

Table 1. Nutrient composition of the organic fertilizer used

S.N.	Nutrients	FYM	Vermicompost	Poultry
1.	N (%)	0.33	1.12	0.84
2.	P (%)	0.25	2.07	1.8
3.	K (%)	0.5	1.8	0.8

Similarly, based on the recommended N equivalent rate for the test crop i.e., 20kgN per ha same quantity of nutrient was applied through FYM, vermicompost and poultry manure.

The fertilizer doses were calculated using the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{g fertilizer/pot} &= \text{kg element / ha} \times \frac{100}{\% \text{ element in the fertilizer}} \times \frac{1}{100\text{m} \times 100\text{m}} \times \frac{1000\text{g}}{1} \times \frac{1}{100\text{cm} \times 100\text{cm}} \times \frac{\text{pot area cm}^2}{1} \\
 &= \text{g fertilizer / pot}
 \end{aligned}$$

Cultural practices were followed as normal as and when required. Growth parameters, yield attributes and yield, nutrient content in seed and straw and residual soil fertility after crop harvest were recorded. Statistical analysis of the data was done in SPSS version bt IBM corporation. The treatment details are given below:

Table 2: Details of treatment and their notations used in the study

Treatment	Description
T1	Control (No fertilizer)
T2	100%N from Poultry Manure @2.4t/ha

T3	100%N from Vermicompost @1.8t/ha
T4	100%N from FYM @6t/ha
T5	Recom.Dose Fert(RDF) (20:40:30 NPK,kg/ha) –No organic fertilizer
T6	50%N from Vermicompost@0.9t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer
T7	50% N from Poultry manure@1.2t/ha+ 50% N from inorganic fertilizer
T8	50%N from FYM @3t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil studies

Soil chemical properties such as pH, organic carbon (OC), N and P were measured for samples taken after harvesting. Significant difference was found in terms of soil available Phosphorus and organic C content by the application of organic and inorganic fertilizers. The result indicated relatively higher P level and OM for pots treated with Farm Yard Manure, poultry manure and vermicompost. The highest P content value 28.87mg/kg was recorded from T3 (100%N from Vermicompost @1.8t/ha) and remained statistically at par with other treatment combination except T1(control). Minimum P content 25.58mg/kg was recorded under treatment T1. Likewise, significantly highest value of OC (3.7%) content was found under treatment T3 (100%N from Vermicompost @1.8t/ha) which remained statistically at par with other treatment combinations except T5 (100% RDF) and T1 (control). Minimum OC content (2.28%) was recorded under T1 and remained at par with T5. Further no statistically significant difference was observed in terms of soil pH and N content among different treatment of organic and inorganic fertilizers. Soil pH values remained unaffected even due to the use of fertilizers applied to may be due to inherent buffering capacity of the soil would also resist small changes in soil pH. Similar results were also reported by (Sikka and Kansal (1995) and Kide et al. (2014). Organic fertilizers may enhanced the crop growth with concomitantly higher root biomass production. It was also supported by Acharya et al. (1988). Benbi et al. (1998) also indicated that the use of organic fertilizer might have made the soil more porous and pulverized, to allow better root growth and development, thereby resulting in higher root cation exchange capacity (CEC). The higher availability of phosphorus in soil due to application of organic fertilizers could be ascribed to mineralization of manures, reduction in fixation and complexing properties of decomposition products of manures

with micronutrients Raddy and Raddy (1998). Higher levels of mineral nutrient in vermin compost and other organic fertilizers treated pots could also be attributed due to chelating action of organic compounds released during decomposition of organic fertilizers which protect these cations from fixation, precipitation, oxidation and leaching Yadav and Kumar (1998).

Table 8. Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on soil chemical properties after crop harvest.

Treatment	pH	N (%)	P (mg/kg)	OC (%)
Control (No fertilizer)	6.44	0.2	25.58 ^a	2.28 ^a
100%N from poultry manure @ 2.4 t/ha	6.6	0.32	28.39 ^b	3.33 ^{bc}
100%N from vermicompost @ 1.8 t/ha	6.7	0.32	28.87 ^b	3.70 ^c
100%N from FYM @ 6 t/ha	6.53	0.303	27.96 ^{ab}	3.13 ^{bc}
Recom. Dose Fert (RDF) (20:40:30 NPK kg/ha) –No organic fertilizer	6.5	0.24	26.77 ^{ab}	2.40 ^a
50%N from vermicompost @ 0.9 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	6.5	0.3	28.23 ^{ab}	3.33 ^{bc}
50% N from poultry manure @ 1.2 t/ha+ 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	6.53	0.31	27.10 ^{ab}	3.00 ^{bc}
50%N from FYM @ 3 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	6.51	0.30	27.93 ^{ab}	3.13 ^{bc}
Mean	6.54	0.29	27.61	3.04
S.Em±	0.03	0.01	0.27	0.10
F test	NS	NS	*	*
LSD	-	-	1.68	0.34
C.V(%)	2.29	20.90	14.70	16.03

*Significant at 0.05 level of probability; NS = Non-significant; Mean values followed by the same letter(s) in a column are not statistically different at 0.05 level of probability (DMRT)

Nutrient content (%)

Application of organic and inorganic fertilizers resulted in significant increase in nitrogen content in seed and straw in comparison with control. Significantly highest values of nitrogen

content in seed and straw were recorded as 3.717 % and 1.377% respectively, under T6(50%N from vermicompost@0.9t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer) and was found statistically at par with all other treatments except T1 Control (No fertilizer). Significantly highest values of phosphorus content in seed and straw were recorded as 0.34 per cent in seed and 0.21 percent in straw under treatment T6 (50%N from vermin compost @ 0.9 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer) and was statistically at par with all other treatment combinations except T4 and T1. The significantly highest values of potassium content in seed and straw were recorded as 1.42 percent in seed and 2.11 percent in straw under treatment T6 (50%N from vermin compost @ 0.9 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer). Data showed that application of 50% N from Vermicompost @ 0.9 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer significantly improved N, P and K content in seed and straw. Increase in nutrient content in plant ascribed to the beneficial role of vermin compost in mineralization of native as well as nutrients in soil through added fertilizers in addition of its own nutrient content which enhanced the available nutrient pool of the soil. The favorable conditions for microbial as well as chemical activities due to addition of above manures in conjunction with fertilizers augmented the mineralization of nutrients and ultimately the available nutrient pool of the soil led to higher uptake of nutrients by plants. Application of nutrients through organic and inorganic sources in combination also recorded significantly higher NPK uptake over the control. Similar results were also obtained by Devi and Agarwal (1999) in sunflower. An improved metabolism to greater translocation of these nutrient to reproductive organs of the crop and ultimately increased the content in seed and straw. These results are in close conformity with those of Vasanthi and Kumarswamy (1999) and Rajkhowa et al. (2000).

Table. Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers in nutrient content (%) in seed and straw

Treatment	Nitrogen content (%)		Phosphorus content (%)		Potassium content (%)	
	Seed	Straw	Seed	Straw	Seed	Straw
	T1 Control (No fertilizer)	2.59 ^a	0.86 ^a	0.16 ^a	0.11 ^a	0.92 ^a
T2 100% N from poultry manure @ 2.4t/ha	3.28 ^{bc}	1.04 ^{ab}	0.25 ^{bc}	0.16 ^{abc}	1.16 ^b	1.55 ^{bc}

T3	100%N from vermicompost @ 1.8t/ha	3.24 ^{bc}	1.11 ^{ab}	0.26 ^{bc}	0.15 ^{abc}	1.17 ^b	1.64 ^{bc}
T4	100% N from FYM @ 6 t/ha	3.07 ^{bc}	0.88 ^a	0.23 ^b	0.14 ^{ab}	1.15 ^b	1.49 ^b
T5	Recom. Dose Fert (RDF) (20:40:30 NPK kg/ha) –No organic fertilizer	3.37 ^{bc}	1.16 ^{abc}	0.29 ^{bc}	0.18 ^{bc}	1.18 ^b	1.78 ^{cd}
T6	50% N from vermicompost @ 0.9 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	3.71 ^c	1.38 ^c	0.34 ^c	0.21 ^c	1.42 ^c	2.12 ^d
T7	50% N from poultry manure @ 1.2 t/ha+ 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	3.50 ^{bc}	1.32 ^{bc}	0.32 ^c	0.19 ^{bc}	1.39 ^c	1.97 ^{cd}
T8	50%N from FYM @ 3 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	3.31 ^{bc}	1.15 ^{ab}	0.27 ^{bc}	0.16 ^{abc}	1.18 ^b	1.79 ^c
	Mean	3.26	1.11	0.27	0.16	1.20	1.67
	S.Em±	0.07	0.04	1.12	0.007	0.03	0.06
	F test	*	*	*	*	*	*
	LSD	0.36	0.21	0.06	0.01	0.12	0.16
	CV%	10.99	18.28	22.48	20.39	13.18	18.88

*Significant at 0.05 level of probability; NS = Non-significant; Mean values followed by the same letter(s) in a column are not statistically different at 0.05 level of probability (DMRT)

Yield attributes and yield

Among the treatments, treatment (T5) (Recom.Dose Fert (RDF) (20:40:30 NPK (kg/ha) recorded maximum 20.52 cm and remained statistically at par with other treatment combinations expect T1 (Control). This may be due to increased supply of major plant nutrients. Nitrogen accelerates the development of growth and reproductive phases and protein synthesis, thus promoting pod length. The findings are in agreement with the findings of Negi et al. (2004). Likewise, Among the treatments T7(50% N from Poultry manure @ 1.2 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer)

recorded maximum 3.93 cm pod weight and remained statistically at par with other treatment expect T1 Control (No fertilizer) and T2 Further, Treatment T6 (50%N from Vermi compost @ 0.9 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer) recorded maximum 9.67 pods per plant. While it was minimum (6.67) under the treatment T1 Control (No fertilizer). The probable reason for enhanced yield may be due to cumulative effects of nutrient (macro and micro) on vegetative growth which ultimately lead to more photosynthetic activities while, application of organic and inorganic fertilizers enhance carbohydrate and nitrogen metabolism of pectic substances, as well as improve the water metabolism and water relation in the plants. Sannigrahi and Borch (2001) observed that the application of FYM @ 20 t/ha + 50% NPK recommended the highest fruit yield in cowpea.

Table 12. Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on yield attributes and yield

Treatment	Pod Length(cm)	Pod weight (gm)	Number of pod per plant	Seed Yield per plant (gm)	Straw yield per plant(gm)
T1: Control (No fertilizer)	2.61 ^a	6.67 ^a	4.76 ^a	10.89	17.26 ^a
T2: 100%N from Poultry Manure @2.4t/ha	2.62 ^a	8.33 ^{ab}	6.78 ^{abc}	11.33	18.29 ^{ab}
T3: 100%N from Vermicompost @1.8t/ha	3.97 ^b	9.33 ^{ab}	8.50 ^c	11.16	18.39 ^{ab}
T4: 100%N from FYM @6t/ha	3.06 ^{ab}	7.67 ^{ab}	5.57 ^{ab}	11.61	18.74 ^{ab}
T5: Recom.Dose Fert(RDF) (20:40:30 NPK,kg/ha) –No organic fertilizer	3.38 ^b	8.67 ^{ab}	8.21 ^{bc}	11.48	20.52 ^b
T6: 50%N from Vermicompost@0.9t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	3.76 ^{ab}	9.67 ^b	9.41 ^c	11.64	20.16 ^b
T7: 50% N from Poultry manure@1.2t/ha+ 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	3.93 ^b	8.67 ^{ab}	6.83 ^{abc}	11.74	19.10 ^{ab}

T8: 50%N from FYM @3t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	3.81 ^b	9.00 ^{ab}	7.00 ^{abc}	11.48	19.31 ^{ab}
Mean	18.97	3.39	8.5	7.14	11.42
S.Em±	0.26	0.13	0.26	0.35	0.32
F test	*	*	*	*	NS
LSD	1.60	0.64	1.77	1.76	-
CV (%)	6.67	18.34	14.72	23.83	13.60

*Significant at 0.05 level of probability; NS = Non-significant; Mean values followed by the same letter(s) in a column are not statistically different at 0.05 level of probability (DMRT)

Growth parameter

Plant height was significantly influenced by the different treatment of organic and inorganic fertilizers. Treatment T6 (50%N from Vermicompost@0.9t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer) recorded maximum 41.56cm plant height. While, it was recorded lowest 35.74 cm in treatment T1 (Control). Likewise, significantly highest number of leaf (31.67) was obtained from treatment T5 (Recom. Dose Fert (RDF) (20:40:30 NPK kg/ha) and remained statistically at par with other treatments expect T1. Fresh weight of root and number of nodules per plant did not vary significantly among treatment. Application of major and minor nutrients, through different levels of organic and inorganic fertilizers, increased the photosynthetic activity, chlorophyll formation, nitrogen metabolism and auxin contents in the plants which ultimately improving the plant height. The finding is also in agreement with the findings (Parasuraman 2001). Number of green leaves per plant increased with increasing levels of N (up to 40 kg N/ha). NPK plays pivotal role in several physiological and biochemical processes, viz., root development, photosynthesis, energy transfer reaction and symbiotic biological N-fixation process. Beneficial effect of FYM, vermin compost and bio fertilizer singly or jointly along with NPK on growth characters of legumes have also been reported by Pathak et. al. (2003).

Table 22. Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on growth parameters

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Number of leaves	Number of nodules/plantsof	Fresh weight of root (g)
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T1	Control (No fertilizer)	35.74 ^a	27.67 ^a	6.00	2.45
T2	100%N from Poultry Manure @ 2.4 t/ha	37.37 ^{ab}	30.33 ^{ab}	7.00	2.67
T3	100%N from Vermicompost @ 1.8 t/ha	37.79 ^{abc}	30.67 ^{ab}	7.67	2.91
T4	100%N from FYM @ 6 t/ha	36.73 ^a	29.33 ^{ab}	6.67	2.78
T5	Recom. Dose Fert (RDF) (20:40:30 NPK kg/ha) –No organic fertilizer	41.40 ^{bc}	31.67 ^b	7.33	3.17
T6	50%N from Vermicompost @ 0.9 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	41.56 ^c	31.33 ^{ab}	8.33	3.21
T7	50% N from Poultry manure @ 1.2 t/ha+ 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	37.07 ^a	31.33 ^b	7.33	3.07
T8	50%N from FYM @ 3 t/ha + 50% N from inorganic fertilizer	36.99 ^a	30.22 ^{ab}	7.67	2.93
	Mean	38.08	30.32	7.25	2.9
	S.Em±	0.49	0.33	0.22	0.12
	F test	*	*	NS	NS
	LSD	2.52	2.16	-	-
	C.V(%)	6.33		5.34	19.58

*Significant at 0.05 level of probability; NS = Non-significant; Mean values followed by the same letter(s) in a column are not statistically different at 0.05 level of probability (DMRT)

CONCLUSION

Addition of organic fertilizer (whether or not inorganic fertilizers included) was found essential to improve soil fertility status in terms of available phosphorus and organic carbon. Eg. vermicompost performed better. With respect to treatment effect on crop growth, combined

application of organic and inorganic fertilizers gave the highest crop growth and biomass yield than sole application of either of organic or inorganic fertilizers. Eg. half vermicompost and half inorganic fertilizer gave maximum growth and biomass yield. Inorganic fertilizers combined with vermicompost was identified as the best treatment for maintaining soil fertility, nutrient uptake at the same time achieving higher crop yields. Under situation when vermicompost is unavailable for farmer inorganic fertilizers could be combine with poultry manure/FYM for similar results.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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